

GEOGRAPHICAL SCIENCES

BASIC PRINCIPLES IN INCREASING THE PRODUCTIVITY OF FORESTS

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Abstract

Among the various natural resources of Azerbaijan, forests occupy the main place. The development of science and technology and the continuous growth of the national economy's need for firewood impose important requirements on the forest enterprise, such as restoration of forest resources, efficient use and increase in productivity. It should be noted that only highly productive forests are able to maintain the environment and increase its wealth. Therefore, one of the important issues of forestry is expanding their areas and increasing their productivity. Solving this valuable task can be done on the basis of developing a system of forestry measures taking into account local conditions.

Keywords: Forest, productivity, gender, species, profitability, reforestation.

Introduction.

Highly productive forests of the future are considered to be programmed forests and form new directions of forest development. First of all, measures to be taken for the cultivation of forests in the future should be carried out on the basis of ecological and economic zoning. Rather, the scientific basis of programmed forests will be the bioecological and bioeconomic understanding of the forest. This is due to the fact that the natural conditions of Azerbaijan have a very diverse character and the forests are unevenly distributed on the territory of the republic. Here there are regions that are completely without forests or the forest cover is not more than 0.5-2% of the total area. The world's population continues to grow, and therefore we must think today about the prosperous life of people in the future and their food supply. From this point of view, the main issue of the modern era is the formation of highly productive forests and the improvement of the natural environment with the help of the system of forestry measures.

Currently, people are worried about the future of the planet and they are trying to ensure that the population is provided with food products, living conditions, and other issues necessary for normal living conditions are resolved. Forests, as a natural complex, being a very complex, qualitatively comprehensive and constantly developing material system, with the characteristic of self-recovery, unlike other means of production, always increase their natural quality and productivity when their use is properly organized. In the conditions of scientific and technical development, it is possible to increase the productivity of forests, protect soils from

erosion, protect them from second salinization, drought, etc., by applying complex measures.

Every year in the Republic of Azerbaijan, a considerable amount of forest restoration, forestry and forest protection measures are carried out, aimed at maintaining and repeatedly restoring forests, increasing their productivity and improving the species composition, and at the same time increasing the positive impact of forests on the environment. However, despite this, the problem of improving the species composition of forests in our country and increasing their productivity will continue to grow, because firewood, which is considered a universal raw material, is increasingly important in the world economy. Here, it is necessary not only to quickly grow firewood stock in a single area, but also to achieve such a breed composition that the quality of their firewood can better meet the needs of various sectors of the national economy. It is difficult to predict what changes will occur in the afforestation process from the period of reforestation to deforestation, or to know what forest products will be obtained. Because this process takes several decades. This problem can be solved only within the framework of a multi-year forecast.

Now it is necessary to make the project "Organization of the development of the forest enterprise" a modern project that stands out from the past projects with its in-depth study and prepares the necessary measures. Such a project should be selected first of all for the novelty of connecting the planned measures with the economy. The program for the cultivation of (productive) forests should be drawn up for a longer period of time, not 10 years as in the past, and the author's

supervision should be carried out constantly. This coincides with the requirements for creating software forests.

When we put forward the concept of complex productivity of forests, it is assumed that it has a number of products, and it is considered the main integral part of the biosphere. Many actions aimed at increasing the growth of trees and improving their condition also lead to the improvement of other beneficial aspects of forests. For example, the construction of field protection forest strips improves the microclimate of the air and soil, makes areas suitable for people to walk, provides additional firewood and fruit crops, etc.

Analysis of results. In order to realize the idea of growing productive forests, the following additional issues need to be resolved: identification of material security, labor resources and other opportunities for forestry production. These issues are not related to biological factors, this aspect of afforestation is related to human economic activities. Human society, which has enormous energy resources at its disposal, is a great force that changes the "face" of nature. Now, other forces, including natural disasters, are already receding into the background. The possibilities of forestry production are really great, either in increasing the productivity and quality of forests, or in obtaining additional nutrients, vitamins, etc. from firewood.

Every important action to be taken must be economically justified. Cultivation of productive program

forests is not an exceptional case here. The main economic indicators of productive forests are the same as other industries: calculated and actual profitability (Lasitski K.B., SimekA.A., 1972).

The main indicator determining profitability for forestry is as follows:

$$\text{Pr} = \frac{N-V}{Z} \times 100$$

Here,

Pr is the calculated bioecological profitability, in %;

N - primary parameters of forest products;

V- the calculated amount of forest products (the time of implementation of measures aimed at the cultivation of program forests);

Z – the total cost of the project of program forests.

The Republic of Azerbaijan is a country with few forests. The forest cover of different regions is different. This diversity is closely related to natural zoning and economic activity of people. If the forest cover in individual regions in the mountain regions is currently 17.59%, the forest cover in the plain regions ranges from 0.65 to 2.0%. The area of forests in the republic is constantly decreasing. In this regard, the per capita forest area and firewood are also decreasing. The main reason for the decline of forest resources is the improper management of people's economic activities and the rapid increase of the population (table 1).

Table 1.

The rate of forest decline

Years	Forest area per capita, hectare	Firewood per person, m ³
1897	0,84	64,0
1913	0,43	53,0
1939	0,31	40,0
1959	0,26	35,6
1970	0,19	24,9
1980	0,16	21,1
1985	0,14	19,2
1990	0,13	18,1
1995	0,12	17,1
2000	0,11	15,8

To analyze any problem of forests, it is first necessary to discover its resources, especially in regions where it is scarce. An important indicator of forest wealth is its species composition, it is with them that the ways of using forest materials and the rate of development of firewood processing are determined.

Changing the species composition of the forests of the Republic of Azerbaijan should be aimed at increasing the wealth of firewood, improving their quality and environmental protection functions. The age structure of forests is also the main indicator in assessing the forests of the republic. They provide information on the area of forests and the supply of firewood for different classes.

Thus, the productivity of Azerbaijan's forests is much lower and due to its level, it does not meet the bioclimatic potential of the regions. This is more clearly visible in the case of individual sexes. For example, each hectare of oak, which is a very valuable

species, has a wood supply of 103 m³, and a sapwood supply of 135 m³. High-yielding and fast-growing species such as poplar and white acacia have 115 and 40 m³ of wood per hectare, respectively. These indicators prove that the reserve of the mentioned tree species is on average 2-3 times lower than the national indicator and 5-6 times lower than standard forests. This is proof of the abnormal management of forestry in the republic. According to what has been said, the main problem of today and the near future is the protection and restoration of forests, for which it is important to develop and implement scientifically based forestry and forest reclamation measures.

The characteristics of forestry should be taken into account when developing a forest forecast. Among them, the following can be noted:

- Forest is a living natural complex (forest biogeocenoses). It develops under the influence of external

environmental conditions. This effect is different depending on the composition of the breed, age, fertility, location in the area.

- Forest resources are classified as renewable resources.

- The forest, like a living organism, changes over time.

- Firewood takes a long time to mature - several decades or more.

- Firewood is the main but not the only product of the forest.

Result.

1. Forest plants of Azerbaijan are one of the most important components of the complex ecosystem. At present, 11% of the territory of the republic is covered with forests, and they are a biological, technological, firewood wealth, as well as an important guarantee of the stabilization of the ecological environment.

2. Changes in the forest cover of the republic are negative. They manifest themselves in the process of reducing the area of forests, replacing the main species of forests with low-value species and non-forest phytocenoses, reducing the density of trees, simplifying their structure, decreasing biological productivity, and weakening the stability of the forest ecosystem.

3. Planting of tree species and groves in places where their biological properties correspond to growing

conditions, selection and seed production of tree species, improvement of forest growing conditions, organization of forestry operations and improvement of roads, maintenance and general use, all of which contribute to increasing the productivity of forests and their environmental protection leads to the improvement of functions.

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